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Adaptation of Generalisation to Linear Intelligent Analytics for Regularisation of PRS

Fatima Isiaka PhD ^{1*} | Zainab Adamu Msc (inview)²

¹ Department of Computer Science
Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Nigeria

² Department of Computer Science
Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria

*** Correspondence:**

FATIMA Isiaka,
Department of Computer Science
Nasarawa State University, Keffi,
Nigeria,

† Present Address:

Department of Computer Science
Nasarawa State University, Keffi,
Nigeria,

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Abstract:

Most measures taken in psychophysiology may include one or more of the following measures: event-related brain potential (ERP), Electrodermal activity (EDA), Skin temperature, Blood pressure, Pupillary measure, and Electroencephalogram (ECG). Each of these measures often comes with a direct connection to the model port of a host machine with an embedded software application for analysis and visualisation. The idea of multimodal capabilities for the analysis of physiological response data is yet to be considered and has a highly prioritised value to analyse datasets generated from experimental studies. This paper attempts to demonstrate the concept by developing a Generalised Linear Intelligent Analytics (GLIA) for a unified physiological response sensor (PRS), the module that generates data embeds a Skin Conductance response measure, Skin temperature measure, Pupil dilation, and Eye movement measure which can be visualised from a single dynamic control system; for this paper, all data are based on a simulated response from the equation model used in the paper and result shows p-values less than 0.09% for predictions of response data using the generalised linear model equation.

Keywords: Electrodermal activity, Pupil changes, Skin temperature, Generalised linear model, Physiological response

1 Introduction

In the field of psychophysiology, the physiological response is the body's automatic response to stimuli, usually when the person is involved in a certain activity [Andreassi (2010); Hugdahl (1995); Kreibig (2010); Freeman (1950); Jacobson (1932); Izard (1993b); Cacioppo et al. (2000); ISIAKA (2023); Devilbiss and Waterhouse (2011); Isiaka et al. (2023)]. Most research focuses on the fact that people are familiar with automatic and instinctive physiological responses experienced in the everyday activity of which they are unaware. These individuals are also prone to more severe physiological responses to stimuli like stress in a person which delves into fight and flight response. When placed in a stressful situation, the participants experience a sweat response in reaction to what they are doing, and the heart rate increases, indicating a reaction to basic stimuli. Sometimes physiological response measures have been known to be an alternative to facial expression to obtain an objective measure of the emotional response that is not prone to modification by the cognitive process of a response to a typical example questionnaire [Izard (1993a); Tourangeau

and Rasinski (1988); Mathews and MacLeod (1994); Krosnick (1991); Hertel and Mathews (2011); Gross (2002); Mathews and MacLeod (2005)]. Examples of physiological response parameters like Skin conductivity (SC), heart rate, Electroencephalography (EEG), and measures of facial muscle activity make use of facial and body muscle shifts to recognise simple emotions.

Most of this physiological response is based on direct response reading from an integrated response model that generates the response from the participants and these readings are visualised on a machine with an installed soft application of the hardware that holds the single response. Data response can be generated from electrodes attached to the hardware [Braithwaite et al. (2013); Shastri et al. (2001); Wan et al. (2021)]. One of the shortcomings is real-time analytics which can be able to analyse these responses based on prediction so that one can know the response of the participant before it can be depicted on a visual machine. This paper uses Generalised Linear Intelligent Analytics (GLIA) for a multi-model physiological response reading and predictions using the Generalised Linear least square (GLLS) for response analysis. The proceeding section discusses the methods and results obtained from the analysis.

$$g(\pi_i) = \sum_{j=1}^p \sum_{i=1}^p \beta_j \times X_{ij} \quad (1)$$

$$\pi \pi_i = E(y = y_i | X = x_i)$$

Where g is the generalised link function, β is the regression coefficients, x is the regression variable, π is the conditional mean as conditional expectations. The expression is based on the following conditions:

$$Z_i = \delta_0 + x_i$$

$$q_i = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(-z_i)} \quad (2)$$

$$y_i \sim \text{Bern}(q_i)$$

Where y_i and z_i are the expected resultant physiological responses from input readings x_i based in environmental factors δ_0 from a Bernoulli conditional value.

2 Method

The pilot study started with designing the GLIA (Figure 1) from the Matlab control toolbox and using a Generalized Linear Model (GLIM, or GLM) for the advanced statistical modelling with the above equations (Equation 1 and 2). The linear regression model for response y is expressed as linear independent observed data from the predicted physiological response. The underlying relationship between the signal input and predicted response is that its linear and outliers are simply removed by a moving average filter. Error distribution of the response is normally distributed before the linear model is built. The generalised link function g allows for the building of the linear relationship between the response and predictor variable even in non-linear cases. All input response reading is based on physiological responses saved in the archive from experiments conducted at the University of Manchester that involve forty participants, with input data based on participants' aggregate responses.

3 Result

Figure 1 shows the index page for the input of physiological response reading and visualisation of the predicted response. The response output parameters such as peak response, amplitude, magnitude, and baseline can also be computed using:

$$P_r = \sum_{i=1}^P \max(x_i) \text{ such that}$$

$$A_r = \max(x_i) i \text{ with}$$

$$M_r = \int_{i=1}^P x_i \quad (3)$$

$$B_i = \int_{i=1}^P \min(x_i)$$

Where P_r , A_r , M_r and B_i are the peak, amplitude, magnitude, and baseline of the input response x_i .

Figure 2 shows a computed generalised linear model for the input signals with input parameters such as the response output skin temperature with contributory parameters such as pupil changes and electrodermal activity (EDA). The

Figure 1: Index page of the GLIA for four different physiological readings.

p-value is seen to be less than 0.009% and a constant model rate of 1.47 based on F-statistics. Each input parameter is based on arbitrary choice depending on the physiological attribute one wants to make predictions on. The GLIA has regulators with included sliders to set parameter options and rate randomisation. The processing speed is based on automated simulation and can be set this too low frequency to easily visualise and comprehend the physiological attributes like the amount of amplitude it takes to get a response peak based on a given magnitude of the response. This way one can easily predict when a response peak will appear and how to deal with the appearance of anomalies. Figure 2 also shows that each input parameter has a p-value less than 0.8% and 0.03% and falls within the average limit for a predicted response. This method can be applied in lie detectors to predict if a person is going to lie about certain interrogative subjective questions for one to know the mood or state of the next interrogation. Error degree of freedom is based on the least mean square value of 0.9%, and quite an authentic score to indicate the level of reliability of the intelligent model.

Figure 2: The window output of the computed Generalised linear regression model.

The linear least square model (LMP), allows for the input of custom parameters in characters or strings instead of making references to default parameters. These parameters can enable future input of more physiological response attributes with an amount of up to a hundred with each attribute indicating the p-values and level of contributions to the given linear model equation.

Figure 3 shows the performance error in terms of model estimation based on feature output response y (skin temperature). For instance, if one wants to predict the skin temperature of a person based on the response from the SCR and Pupil changes, we can visualize the response as skin temperature and visually synchronize it with input real-time SCR and Pupil dilation. This is one of the contributions of the work, the ability to generate an additional physiological response to the set of available readings. At this level of prediction, one can also generate the emotional expression of a person without actually looking at the person. The four user attributes from Figure 3 can be related

to EEG, ECG, heart rate, and ERR. These parameters can also serve as predicted responses provided the number of input parameters is more than the maximum limit specified for the engine, which could be limitless.

Figure 3: Performance of response attribute on input parameters x1, x2, x3, x4 and x5.

Figure 4 shows the response parameters and corresponding input parameters of the model with p-values less than 0.01% and falls within the range of authentic response performance for the model. The form output is a page on the generalised linear regression model that doesn't allow for the input of custom string variables. It sets a default value of x and ranges from $I = 1, \dots, n$ depending on the limit set for the input parameters. The chi-square statistics has a model value of 2.04 and can be visualised in real-time simulation mode. Each of the p-values is based on Poisson distribution a simple and standard procedure.

Figure 4: Window output for response parameters and corresponding input parameters.

Figure 5 shows the response diagram of the predicted skin temperature from the input parameter pupil changes, this is based on $\frac{170}{100}\mu s$ (-0.13% and 0.13%) error detection rate. The last error is set at $\frac{10}{100}\mu s$ (-0.01% and 0.01%), this is less than the maximum error limit for a given response value and establishes a genuine authenticity for the GLIA. The response also shows that the data is normally distributed and indicates the GLM is an appropriate choice of model to analyse the physiological response attributes.

4 Conclusion

This paper seeks to model the physiological response data (PRD) by adaptation of generalisation to linear intelligent analytics for the regularisation of PRD. The paper attempts to demonstrate the concept by the development of a Generalised Linear Intelligent Analytics (GLIA) for a unified physiological response sensor (PRS), the module that generates the data embeds a Skin Conductance response measure, Skin temperature measure, Pupil dilation, and Eye

Figure 5: Response output result for predicted skin temperature and input parameter pupil changes.

movement measure which can be visualised from a single dynamic control system; for this paper, all data is based on the simulated response from the equation model used in the paper and the result shows p-values less than 0.09% for predictions of response data using the generalised linear model equation. The response prediction also indicates that the data is normalised and GLIA is a reliable model for predicting physiological response parameters. The future perspective would be to use linear models and Bernoulli's principles to test their compatibility with quantified cognitive response values and set a data model for the prediction of the conscious cognitive response of a person.

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About the Authors

Fatima Isiaka The author had her PhD in Computer Science at Sheffield Hallam University, United Kingdom, in 2017, She taught briefly for a year as a lecturer assistant at the University of Manchester. She obtained her Master's degree from the Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi, Benue state, in 2009 and earned a first degree in Mathematics in 2004 from Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi. She majored mostly in Data mining, Artificial intelligence design, Human Factors, and Human-Computer Interactions. Her main interests include writing publications, programming with JAVA, Matlab, R, VB.net, writing scripts for play right, and coding. Her free time is spent playing with the kids and cooking.

Zainab Adamu Had her Master in Computers at the Nasarawa State University, Keffi. She had her first degree in Computer Science at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Nigeria. Her major interest is coding, design, writing literature, and editing. She majored mostly in Human factors, Human-computer interactions, User interphase design, programming, and knowledge acquisition. During her leisure, she enjoys fabric design, cooking, and going for a walk outdoors with the kids.

